

THE OBJECTIVES OF DRAMATIZATION ACTIVITIES IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTION

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ABSTRACT

Dramatization activities are a key tool for developing empathy, as they facilitate the organization of children's collaborative activities and allow them to actively engage with social reality, artistic works, and fairy tales, thereby acquiring social behavioral skills. As a result, children come to understand the world intellectually and emotionally, forming attitudes towards good and evil. They learn to indirectly resolve many problematic situations through the perspective of a character, overcoming difficulties in communication and shyness.

INTRODUCTION

Today, the issue of preschool education and upbringing is being addressed on a broad and fundamental scale. The tasks facing preschool educators are becoming increasingly complex, and the task of introducing children to dramatization and theatrical activities from an early age is becoming very important. Dramatization activities and the development of an individual's creative abilities are an integral part of the socio-economic and spiritual directions of modern social structures. The word "creativity" in a social context refers to the search and representation of something new, which has not been encountered in past experiences, both on an individual and social level. Creative activity is the process of generating something new; it is the free art of creating a new product that reflects the personal "self." Creativity is not only about creating new things in material and spiritual culture, but also about the improvement of the individual, particularly in the spiritual domain. The world surrounding a child largely determines their mood, shaping their attitudes toward objects, actions, and even themselves. A child learns about the surrounding world through their visual (visual analyzer), auditory (auditory analyzer), and motor (motor analyzer) senses. This means that everything around the child must develop these senses and provide the necessary psychological comfort.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Children's creativity is one of the pressing issues in preschool pedagogy and child psychology. This topic has been explored in-depth by L.S.Vygotsky, A.N.Leontiev and others. Engaging in dramatization activities not only introduces children to the world of beauty but also awakens their sense of compassion and empathy, stimulates cognitive curiosity, and most importantly, liberates their creative potential, helping them adapt psychologically to the

group. According to Yu.A. Tsapkova, dramatization activities are aimed at developing emotions (sensations), feelings, emotions, thinking, imagination, fantasy, attention, memory, will, and numerous skills (speech, communication, organization, mobility, etc.) in participants.

“Theater is a beautiful art. It ennobles and educates the human soul. A person who truly loves theater always carries away wisdom and compassion.” Dramatization and theatrical elements are identified by their similarity to an actor’s performance, as studied by Konstantin Stanislavski, who also found similarities in the emotional engagement of children participating in theatrical games. This emotional engagement encompasses both the actor's and the child's feelings and sensations. M.N.Makhaneva has discussed the educational potential of dramatization activities in detail. By participating in staged performances, children familiarize themselves with the external world and its diversity through images, colors, and sounds. Thought-provoking questions compel them to think, analyze, draw conclusions, and generalize. In the context of preschool education, attention must be given to theatrical activities such as:

- Watching puppet theater and discussing it;
- Dramatization games;
- Preparing and performing various fairy tales;
- Exercises to develop expressive performance;
- Special exercises for analyzing artistic works;
- Exercises aimed at the social and emotional development of children.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Dramatization activities in preschool institutions aim to improve unconventional methods and techniques for stimulating children's imagination and creative thinking. Recommendations for creating conditions that promote the development of role-playing dialogic and monologic speech abilities in children during storytelling and performance are suggested.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The primary objectives of dramatization activities in preschool education include:

1. Creating conditions for dramatization activities in accordance with the state standards of preschool education (creating various types of theaters, decorations, screens, and catalogs of theatrical games).
2. Introducing children to different types of theater in a structured manner; the repertoire should consist of staged performances based on fairy tales, children's literature, classical plays for children, and plays suitable for children. There are dramatic types (children’s theater) and puppet theater.
3. Enriching and activating children’s vocabulary, introducing them to key theatrical terms such as: Theater, Playwright, Director, Orchestra, Conductor, Composer, Actor, Puppet Theater, etc.
4. Developing children's communication skills: enhancing their ability to communicate with both adults and peers, promoting role-playing dialogues during fairy tale performances based on the rules of oral communication.
5. Fostering children's theatrical and creative skills, and developing skills in theatrical culture, such as intonation, gestures, mimicry, pantomime, diction, tempo, and vocal strength.

6. Teaching children to create puppet theater characters using additional materials like cardboard, matchboxes, tennis balls, plastic spoons, disposable tableware, socks, gloves, plastic bottles, natural materials, etc.

To develop dramatization activities, educators must ensure that children listen attentively to artistic speech from an early age, emotionally engage with it, and be guided toward creative dialogues, rhymes, songs, and poems.

- Developing children's interest in dramatization activities by creating opportunities for puppet theater characters to interact with children and display scenes.

- Ensuring that the necessary stage equipment for dramatization activities is in place, including purchasing theatrical toys, creating toys by hand, costumes, decorations, and attributes.

- Paying special attention to the selection of literary works for dramatization: these should be understandable for children, possess moral ideas, feature dynamic events, colorful characters, and positive traits.

WORK WITH CHILDREN

The work on teaching children dramatization activities should be carried out in four directions:

1. **With educators:**

- Conversations
- Consultations
- Open sessions, seminar workshops
- Business games
- Roundtable discussions

2. **With children:**

- Watching puppet theaters and discussing them
- Dramatization games, musical games
- Exercises for social and emotional development
- Diction exercises (articulation gymnastics)
- Transformation games (pantomimes)
- Finger training games to develop fine motor skills
- Tasks to develop speech intonation (diction, rhythm, tone, tempo)
- Staging various fairy tales and stories

Creating a developmental environment and establishing a constantly changing atmosphere is essential for organizing various forms of work with children in preschool institutions. This includes:

- Art centers, plot-role-playing games, and dramatization centers;
- Educational and developmental games;
- Attributes for role-playing games;
- Children's literature;
- A catalog of poems, fairy tales, stories, riddles, songs, and proverbs;
- Scripts for holiday events;
- Recreational moments.
- A "Theater" mini-museum.
- Open sessions.

Role-playing games and dramatization centers are organized in groups, considering the developmental characteristics of children. Special areas are set up for directing games using finger theaters, table theaters, shadow theaters, marionette theaters, glove puppet theaters, costume theaters, and more.

CONCLUSION

Thus, dramatization activities help develop children's self-confidence and enable each child to express themselves in various roles, fostering the development of social behavioral skills. Educators should use various techniques such as:

- Allowing children to choose roles according to their preferences;
- Assigning roles not only to brave children but also to shy or introverted ones;
- Distributing roles through cards depicting characters;

Allowing all children to take turns playing different roles.

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